

Green-synthesis and physico-chemical characterization of silver nanoparticles fabricated from *Sellaginella tamariscina* (Beauv.) Spring.

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Abstract— Silver nanoparticles (SNPs) were bio-fabricated via aqueous plant extract of *Sellaginella tamariscina* (Beauv.) Spring. The optimum parameters for the synthesis of SNPs were 3 mM AgNO₃ concentration, 5 ml of extract volume, pH 9 and time 30 min. The synthesized SNPs were characterized through UV-visible spectroscopy, Fourier transform infra-red spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). UV-vis study showed a distinctive peak at 440 nm which indicated the formation of nanoparticles. FTIR study specified the participation of the phenolic compounds, carboxylic acid, amino acids and other phytochemicals for the synthesis and the stabilization of the SNPs. XRD revealed the crystalline size which was 11.57nm. SEM analysis informed the spherical shape and average particle size (69.88 nm) of SNPs.

Key words —Silver nanoparticles, *Sellaginella tamariscina*, green chemistry, Fourier transform infra-red spectroscopy (FTIR), X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

1. INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is a developing ground of research which involves a numerous application such as antimicrobial, materials for food packaging, drug delivery of medicines and also persona care products [1]. Nanoparticles are contemplated as a link between atomic structures and bulk materials. Among the nanoparticles gold and silver nanoparticles have gained extensive interests for their various application in modern scientific field [1]. Furthermore, silver nanoparticles (SNPs) have great antioxidant as well as high antimicrobial properties [2]. In recent time the Bio-fabrication of nanoparticles have established a considerable attention because of its eco-friendly approach over the physical and chemical methods. These methods produce toxic wastes and costly due to high energy requirement in contrary the green methods of nanoparticle synthesis are both sustainable and cost-effective process [3]. In the green method different types of biomolecules like bacteria, fungi, algae, enzymes and biodegradable polymers have been used in the construction of metallic nanoparticles. [4],[5],[6]. As the plants contains a number of bioactive molecules that can use as reducing and stabilizing agents for synthesis of metal nanoparticles which is also suitable for large scale production. Additionally, Phyto-synthesis of nanoparticles rejects problems like microbial culture maintenance, and long incubation period.

In the present study plant extract of *Sellaginella tamariscina* (Beauv.) Spring is used for the fabrication of SNPs. *S. tamariscina* is an evergreen perennial herb belongs to the Selaginellaceae family with high ethnomedicinal values in herbal medicine that treats gastro-intestinal hemorrhage, cough, regular menstrual cycle and cure wounds [7]. Adnan et al. [8] mentioned about different phenolic contents and two new natural pigments Selaginellin A and B from *S. tamariscina* and their applications in different therapeutic fields. In the present experiment, we reported the fruitful and sustainable synthesis of SNPs using aqueous extract of *S. tamariscina* and their characterization.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Preparation of plant extract

Healthy and fresh plants of *S. tamariscina* was collected from Sillery Gaon, **Height**-6000ft, **Latitude**-27.1396°N, **Longitude**-88.5804°E, Kalimpong, West Bengal, India. The Collected plants are washed in tap water to eliminate the dust and soil particles. Clean plants are shed dried in room temperature. The ten grams of plants were taken with 100 ml of ddH₂O in a beaker and boiled at 60° C for 30 min. The plant extract was filtered initially by a clean muslin cloth and finally by Whatman filter paper, Grade 1 (Merk). The filtered aqueous extract was kept at 4° C for the following uses.

2.2. Green synthesis of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs)

Bio-synthesis of silver nanoparticles was done following the method described by to Sinha and Paul [9] with some modifications. 45 ml of AgNO₃ of different concentrations (1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 mM) mix with different volume of plant extract (1, 3, 5, 7 and 9 ml) separately to detect the optimum AgNO₃ concentration and plant extract volume optimized for bio-fabrication of nanoparticles. To detect the optimum pH for nanoparticle synthesis reaction was also conducted at different pH (5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11). To investigate the optimum reaction time for SNP synthesis experiment was done in various time intervals (5min, 30min, 122min and 180min). Each reaction mixture was kept in room temperature in dark place. The formation of dark brown colour in solution mixture indicated formation of silver nanoparticles. The absorption spectra of each sample were taken at 300-700 nm. The SNP solution was centrifuged at 15000 rpm for 15 min. The supernatant was thrown away and the pellet was dispersed again in deionized water.

2.3 Phytochemical screening of aqueous extract of *S. tamariscina*

Qualitative phytochemical screening was performed according to the methods described by Harborne [10] such as phenols, flavonoids, tannins, terpenoids, saponins, glycosides, Cardiac glycosides, alkaloids Coumarins, quinones, Anthocyanins, carbohydrates and proteins

2.4. Characterization of fabricated silver nanoparticles

The synthesized nanoparticles were characterized with the following techniques

2.4.1. UV-visible spectroscopy analysis

A small portion of synthesized SNPs were diluted in deionized water and experimented through UV-vis spectrophotometric analysis (Lasany® L1-3001) to confirm the reduction of metal ion (Ag^+) and scanned between 200-500 nm wavelength at a resolution of 1 nm.

2.4.2. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis

SEM was performed to examine the shape and size of silver nanoparticles using Scanning electron microscope (FEI-Quanta FEG 200F) accessorized with EDX. A tiny drop of SNP solution was applied on a carbon-coated copper grid and then it was dried by keeping it below a mercury lamp for few minutes. EDX study was done to determine the different elements present in the SNPs along with silver.

2.4.3. X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurement

XRD performance was used to disclose crystalline nature and crystalline size of bio-synthesized SNPs through XRD (Bruker, D8 DISCOVER) and scanned was accomplished in 2θ ranging from 30 to 80°. The XRD pattern was recorded by $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation with a wavelength of 1.5406 Å functioned at a voltage of 40 kV, 40 mA. The crystalline size was analyzed by ebye-Scherrer equation, crystalline size (D) = $\frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta}$, k is Scherrer constant, β is FWHM (full width half maximum), λ is wavelength of the X-ray source.

2.4.4. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy measurements

The dried SNPs were examined by FTIR spectroscopy (Perkin Elmer FTIR Model L120-00A) in the range of 500–4000 cm^{-1} .to detect the probable biochemical groups were present on the surface of nanoparticles in stabilization and capping of the silver nanoparticles.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Phytochemical screening of extract of *S. tamariscina*

The aqueous leaf extract of *S. tamariscina* tested positive for the phytochemicals like Phenols, Flavonoids, Alkaloids, steroids, Saponins, Coumarins, Quinones, Carbohydrate and Protein (Table 1). Liu et al. [11] estimated flavonoids from *S. tamariscina*. In Their work they also stated the presence of phenolics, Steroids and Alkaloids in leaf extracts.

Table 1 Phytoconstituents of aqueous leaf extract *S. tamariscina*

Sl. No.	Name of the Phytochemicals	Result	Sl. No.	Name of the Phytochemicals	Result
1.	Phenols	+++	8.	Coumarins	+
2.	Tannins	-	9.	Quinones	+
3.	Flavonoids	++	10.	Anthocyanins	-
4.	Alkaloids	+	11.	Glycosides	-
5.	Steroids	+	12.	Cardiac glycosides	-
6.	Terpenoids	-	13.	Carbohydrates	+
7.	Saponins	+	14.	Protein	+

+ denotes presence or positive reaction; ++ denotes the presence in higher degree;

- denotes absence or negative reaction

3.2. UV-vis spectroscopy analysis of synthesized SNPs

The optimum parameters for the synthesis of SNPs were 3 mM AgNO_3 concentration, 5ml of extract volume, pH 9 and time 30 min. UV-vis study showed a characteristic peak at 440 nm which indicated the formation of well dispersed nanoparticles (Figure 1). In acidic pH the colour of the reaction mixture was light directed the lower formation of nanoparticles. With gradual increases in the pH (pH 9) the solution mixture became darker specified the higher degree of SNPs formation. At higher pH (10, 11) there was a shift in the peak towards higher wavelength indicating the agglomeration of nanoparticles. This result is also supported by many researchers [12], [13]. They stated pH 9 as optimum pH for the synthesis of SNPs.

Figure 1: UV-vis spectrum of SNPs: (A) at 3 mM AgNO₃ concentration, 5 ml of plant extract volume, pH 9 room and temperature;

(B) at 3 mM, 3 mM AgNO₃ concentration, 5 ml of plant extract volume, pH 9, room temperature at different time intervals.

3.3 FTIR study of synthesized AgNPs

The FT-IR spectrum of *S. tamariscina* aqueous extract and the synthesized nanoparticles was compared to disclose the functional groups from the extracts involved in the bio-reduction process to synthesize silver nanoparticles. The FTIR study of extract and SNPs (**Figure 2 A and B**) presented a broad peak at 3400.99 cm⁻¹ arising due to vibrational frequencies of -OH group from phenolic compounds present in the extract while the FT-IR spectrum study of synthesized nanoparticles exhibited a narrow peak at 3423.54 cm⁻¹, that might be as a result of new interactions between the extract and silver (Ag⁺). The absorption bands at 2930.50 cm⁻¹ (extract) and 2924.85 cm⁻¹ (SNPs) were assigned to the stretching vibration of alkanes. Another prominent peaks at 1601.48 cm⁻¹ (extract) and 1631.54 cm⁻¹ (SNPs) were attributed to NH bending from amino acids. The peaks at 1400.91 cm⁻¹ (extract) and 1381.87 cm⁻¹ (SNPs) were contributed to the carboxyl group. The absorption bands near 1078.32 cm⁻¹ (extract) and 1055.71 cm⁻¹ (SNPs) were ascribed to C-N stretching vibration of aliphatic amines. A new peak raised almost near 2600 cm⁻¹ of FT-IR spectrum of the fabricated SNPs which was absent in the extract. This result signifying the new probable interaction between extract and metal silver. These absorption peaks established the involvement of biomolecules like phenolic compounds, amino acids, carboxylic acid and other phytochemicals in the capping and stabilization of SNPs. In the present study the result was corroborated with the FTIR study of bio-synthesized SNPs from different plant materials by a number of researchers [14], [15], [16].

(B)

Element	Weight %	Atomic %
O	07.88	29.54
Mg	02.26	05.58
Cl	13.10	22.17
Ag	76.76	42.71

Figure 2: FTIR- spectrum (A) plant extract (B) synthesized nanoparticles

3.4 X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of synthesized nanoparticles

The XRD study of fabricated SNPs revealed the different diffraction angles (2θ) at 27.59, 32.32, 38.72, 44.12, 64.28, 77.35 with their corresponding plane orientations (**Figure 3**). The peaks 38.72, 44.12, 64.28, 77.35 are indexed to 111, 200, 220, 311 planes of silver which stated the crystalline nature of SNPs and two peaks 27.59, 32.32 specified the cubic phase of silver chloride [17]. The crystalline size was calculated from strong peak (111) near 38.72 value which was 11.57nm. XRD analysis indicated the presence of AgCl which may form by the excess silver ion in the reaction mixture with the chloride present in the extract. Furthermore, strong peak of silver than the silver chloride indicated the purity of the synthesized nanoparticles. Kedi et. al [14] described supported the result in their XRD investigation of silver nanoparticles fabricated from *Selaginella myosurus*.

Figure 3: X-ray diffraction analysis of synthesized AgNPs

3.5. SEM and EDX of synthesized nanoparticles

SEM analysis displayed the nanoparticle agglomeration in the image which was composed of small spherical nanoparticles (**Figure 4 A**). The average particle size measured was 69.88 nm. The XRD analysis specified the smaller crystalline size that might be due to the multi crystalline nature of the SNPs or due to the fact that XRD study involves deeper analysis than the SEM analysis where only surface particles were measured. Asif et al. [18] concluded the similar finding in their experiment where the SEM image unveiled the agglomeration of nanoparticles fabricated from *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract. EDX is similarly very useful in determining the existence of other elements in the sample. It also illustrates the qualitative as well as quantitative elemental analysis of the synthesized SNPs. The EDX spectrum (**Figure 4 B**) shows that nanoparticles were largely comprised of O, Mg, Cl, Ag (76.76 %). EDX spectrum displayed strong characteristic signal peak of metallic silver closely at 3 KeV (**Figure 4 B**).

Figure 4: (A) SEM image of synthesized SNPs; (B) Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectrum of SNP showing percentage of different elements along with metal silver

4. CONCLUSION

The plant extract mediated synthesis of SNPs is an ecofriendly and rapid process to construct SNPs. Additionally, it is also a green, inexpensive and high yield approach. Reduction was probably done by phytochemicals like phenolic compounds, amino acids and carboxylic acid. Additional studies need to be done to comprehend the precise mechanism of nanoparticle formation in order to have an improved regulation over the shape and size of SNPs. Moreover, this green synthesized SNPs can be further studied for their antioxidant and antimicrobial potential since they were synthesized from plant with high ethnomedicinal properties.

DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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